

STUDIES IN CHROMIUM OXIDE SOLS. PART I. ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CHROMIUM OXIDE SOL

BY A.K.M. TRIVEDI, C. S. BHATT AND A. S. DIVATIA

Concentrated chromium oxide sols were prepared by adding ammonium carbonate solution to a boiling concentrated solution of chromium chloride. The sols were purified by hot dialysis and the various constituents were analysed. The sols were diluted with water and the electrical conductivity of the diluted sols was determined. It has been found that, (a) the specific conductivity of the sol decreases on dialysis, (b) the equivalent conductivity of the micelles is much smaller than that of the stabilising electrolyte, if it is present in a free condition, and (c) the chromium oxide sol shows the behaviour of a typical colloidal electrolyte.

McBain (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1279) has pointed out that one of the characteristic properties of soaps and similar paraffin chained electrolytes is that at relatively high concentrations, the equivalent conductivity of the micelles increases with increase in concentration. Hartley ("Aqueous Solutions of Paraffin Chain Salts," 1936, p.2; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 1284; *Kolloid Z.*, 1939, 88, 22) has suggested that the theory should apply to any inorganic colloidal system in which the particles are charged by the adsorption of ions. This was also found to be true in the case of sulphur sols (Bolam and Trivedi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1943, 39, 247) and iron oxide sols (Trivedi, Divatia and Patani, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, 36A, 530). In the present investigation, it has been pointed out that in the case of well-dialysed chromium oxide sols, the adsorption of ions on the micelles leads to decreased dissociation of the adsorbed ions. Again, the conductivity of the micelles increases with increase in concentration within a certain range, depending upon the purity of the sol. It has also been found that, in general, the charge decreases on dialysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chromium oxide sols were prepared after Mitra and Dhar (*this Journal*, 1932, 9, 315). A concentrated solution of chromium chloride (green variety) was boiled and 14% ammonium carbonate solution was gradually added from a burette with constant stirring until a slight precipitate was formed. The sol, thus prepared, was purified by continuous hot dialysis after Neidle and Barab (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1962; 1917, 39, 71). The purified sols were carefully evaporated on a water-bath at 60° till the desired concentration was obtained.

The solid content of the sol was obtained by evaporating the sol in an oven at 120°-134°. Chloride was estimated by Mohr's method, after coagulating the sol with potassium sulphate. The analysis of the sols used for the experiments is shown below.

TABLE I

Sol.	Total solid content (g./litre).	Chloride (g./litre).	Chloride (g.e./litre).	Chromium chloride (g./litre).	Chromium oxide (g./litre).	Purity ratio.
A	60.40	7.021	0.19800	10.450	40.950	7.114
B	42.70	3.333	0.09399	4.962	37.738	11.330

The final column in Table I shows the purity ratio expressed as chromium oxide/chloride.

The electrical conductivity of the sols, diluted to different extents, was measured as before (Trivedi, Divatia and Patani *loc. cit.*); 50 ml. of the sol was taken and 50 ml. of water was added. This was termed 0.5C sol. Similarly 0.9C, 0.8C, etc. sols were prepared. The dilution was made with conductivity water (1.5×10^{-6} mhos), the conductivity of water being considered negligible in comparison with the conductivity of the sols, under examination. In each case, several readings of resistances were obtained which differed by less than 0.3%. Table II records the mean values of the resistances.

TABLE II

Conc. of the sols.	Resistance.	Sp. condy. of the micelles.	Equiv. condy. of micelles. (a)	Equiv. condy. of free chromium chloride. (b)	Ratio a/b.
Sol A.					
100%	29.14	7.452×10^{-3}	37.63	91.2	0.412
90	32.56	6.670	37.43	93.0	0.402
80	37.20	5.838	36.85	95.0	0.387
70	43.60	4.980	35.92	98.0	0.366
60	52.20	4.160	35.01	100.0	0.350
50	64.22	3.383	34.18	104.0	0.328
40	83.15	2.611	32.97	108.0	0.305
30	110.76	1.963	33.06	114.0	0.290
20	162.10	1.340	33.84	122.0	0.277
10	267.30	0.812	41.04	135.0	0.304
Sol B.					
100	64.14	3.386×10^{-3}	36.02	104.8	0.343
90	72.98	2.976	35.18	107.0	0.328
80	83.88	2.589	34.43	109.0	0.315
70	100.05	2.172	33.01	112.0	0.294
60	122.16	1.778	32.54	115.0	0.274
	149.83	1.450	30.86	119.0	0.259
50	196.26	1.107	29.44	123.0	0.239
40	265.36	0.818	29.05	128.0	0.227
30	410.50	0.529	28.16	135.8	0.207
20	524.66	0.413	29.38	141.0	0.208
10	655.03	0.331	35.28	149.0	0.236

DISCUSSION

The specific conductivity (k) of the sol is calculated after calculating the specific conductivity of potassium chloride at 35°, as obtained by plotting the values of the specific conductivity of potassium chloride at different temperatures (Jones and Bardshaw, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1780). The chromium oxide sol may contain, besides the gegenions, free NH_4^+ ions, free H^+ ions, free Cr^{3+} ions and free Cl^- ions. The sol was coagulated and the presence of NH_4^+ ions was tested by Nessler's reagent. It was found to be absent. Similarly, the filtrate and the washings after coagulating the sol showed no acidity. The absence of acidity in the case of chromium oxide sol was confirmed by Bassett and Durrant (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 277) and Yoe and Freyer (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1389). Free Cr^{3+} ions were tested by diphenylcarbazide reagent (Stover, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2363). A slight pink colour was obtained, indicating that there was only a trace of free Cr^{3+} ions in the sol. Therefore, the well-dialysed sols used in the conductivity experiments contain practically no other electrolytes except the gegenions. Assuming that the conductivity of the sol is due to micelles only, the equivalent conductivity (Λ) of the micelles can be found out by the formula,

$$\Lambda = \frac{1000 k}{c}$$

where c is the concentration of the chloride in g. ions/litre and k is the specific conductivity of the micelles. The molecular conductivity of chromium chloride, if it is existing in a free condition, is obtained by following the data of Winston and Jones (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1911, 46, 396). The equivalent conductivity will be one third the molecular conductivity. Table II shows the equivalent conductivity of the micelles and of chromium chloride, if it was existing in a free condition.

It is found that in all cases the equivalent conductivity of the micelles is much smaller than the conductivity of free chloride, the actual ratio being 20% to 40%. Bjerrum (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 110, 676) studied the osmotic pressure and membrane potential in the case of chromium oxide sol and concluded that about 90% of the chloride ions was adsorbed on the chromium oxide micelles. Rinde (*Phil. Mag.*, 1926, vii, 1, 49) had recalculated Bjerrum's values for membrane potentials and concluded that the true value was somewhat lower, about 75%.

The behaviour of chromium oxide sol is similar to that of sulphur sol (Bolam and Trivedi, *loc. cit.*), iron oxide sol (Trivedi, Divatia and Patani, *loc. cit.*) and stannic oxide sol (Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2290). Actually, in the case of chromium oxide sol, the degree of dissociation of gegenions comes out to about 25%, which is higher than the corresponding values obtained in the case of sulphur sol, iron oxide sol and stannic oxide sol. The higher value actually obtained (final column in Table II) may be due to the fact that the sol may contain free electrolyte, not allowed for in the calculations. At any rate, it may be concluded that the bulk of the stabilising electrolyte adheres to the micelles.

The sol A was dialysed for 20 days, its purity ratio being 7.114. The B sol was dialysed for 35 days, its purity ratio being 11.330. Table III records the conductivity of the same concentration in the case of the sols A and B.

TABLE III

Conc. of the sol (chromium oxide). ro g./litre	Sp. conductivity.	
	Sol A.	Sol B.
20	1.20×10^{-3}	0.41×10^{-3}
30	2.19	1.03
30	3.30	2.11
40	4.62	3.12

Thus, in general, the specific conductivity of the sol decreases on dialysis. This is in agreement with Chakravarti and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1646) who conclude that as hydrophilic sols are dialysed, the charge decreases. If we compare the variation of the conductivity of the micelles on dilution with the variation of the conductivity of free chromium chloride on dilution, a striking point is noticed. While in the case of free chromium chloride, the equivalent conductivity increases with dilution, in the case of the sol, the conductivity of the micelles first decreases with dilution and then increases with further dilution. This is shown, graphically in the case of sol B, where equivalent conductivity is plotted against $\sqrt{c}$. The

FIG. 1

behaviour of chromium oxide sol is in harmony with the behaviour of sulphur sol (Bolam and Trivedi, *loc. cit.*) and iron oxide sol (Trivedi, Divatia, and Patani, *loc. cit.*). The similarity to soap solutions (McBain, *loc. cit.*) is obvious. It may therefore be concluded that the decrease in equivalent conductivity with dilution may take place in any inorganic colloidal system, provided that the conditions are suitable. Hence, such systems may be classified amongst colloidal electrolytes.

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